

MULTIVARIATE SUCCESS INDICATORS OF PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS PERFORMANCE IN SCIENCE AMONG GRADE 8 STUDENTS IN MOGPOG, MARINDUQUE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12559113>

ABSTRACT

One dimension to helping students is to find comparatively better way of teaching; that is the way Science is presented to students. This study aims to investigate the multivariate success indicators of problem-solving performance in science among grade eight students towards the development of proposed Science activities. Specifically, it aims to determine the problem solving performance of grade 8 students in Science; establish any significant relationship between science beliefs, Science attitudes, Science self-efficacy and metacognitive skills on science problem-solving performance among grade eight students; identify any multivariate success indicators in problem solving performance in science among grade eight students in terms of Science Beliefs; Attitudes towards Science; Science Self-Efficacy; and Metacognitive Skills and propose a framework with activities integrated relevant to structured problem-solving approach. The independent variables in this study are the multivariate indicators while the dependent variable is the performance of the students. Descriptive-correlational was used as the research design of the study to determine the multivariate success indicators of problem-solving performance in science among 140 grade eight students. The analysis revealed a concerning picture of Grade 8 students' science problem-solving performance. A significant portion (47.14%) failed to meet expectations, with no students reaching the "Outstanding" level. This highlights a pressing need for intervention and improvement. The research found a critical link between students' science beliefs and their problem-solving abilities. Those with strong convictions about the nature and value of science demonstrated significantly better performance. This underscores the importance of fostering such beliefs, potentially through activities exploring the nature of science and its real-world applications. While attitudes towards science, science self-efficacy, and metacognitive skills did not directly correlate with problem-solving performance, they may

still play indirect roles or require further investigation in specific contexts. Exploring domain-specific confidence and strategic thinking skills in science could yield valuable insights for future research and intervention strategies. Based on these findings, several activities could be integrated into a structured problem-solving approach. Cultivating science beliefs through case studies, debates, and field trips, introducing domain-specific metacognitive strategies, and promoting collaborative learning through peer discussions and shared problem-solving tasks could empower students to become confident and effective science problem-solvers.

Keywords: *education; problem-solving, skill performance, success indicator, science, grade 8 students, structured problem-solving*

INTRODUCTION

Effective problem-solving lies at the heart of scientific inquiry and is a crucial component of scientific literacy (Chin & Osborne, 2010; NRC, 2012). Beyond mere knowledge acquisition, students need to develop the skills to analyze information, formulate hypotheses, design experiments, interpret data, and draw conclusions—a complex cognitive repertoire essential for navigating the dynamic landscape of scientific exploration (Scardamalia & Bereiter, 2006).

However, research suggests that many students struggle with scientific problem-solving (OECD, 2019). Studies indicate that while students may possess basic factual knowledge, they often lack the ability to apply this knowledge effectively to novel situations or solve complex problems (Bell et al., 2003; Tai et al., 2006). This gap between knowledge and application raises concerns about the adequacy of current science education approaches and underscores the need for deeper understanding of factors that influence successful problem-solving in science.

Identifying the key psychological constructs that underpin successful problem-solving in science necessitates a multifaceted approach that moves beyond solely examining cognitive skills. Recent research highlights the critical role of non-cognitive factors such as science beliefs, attitudes, self-efficacy, and metacognitive skills in influencing students' engagement with, and mastery of, scientific inquiry (Osborne et al., 2003; Schraw & Moshman, 2002).

Science beliefs: Studies suggest that strong, positive beliefs about the nature and value of science are associated with increased engagement, motivation, and perseverance in problem-solving tasks (Kuhn et al., 2010; Sinatra & Pintrich, 2003). Students who view science as an open-ended, collaborative effort of inquiry are more likely to approach problems with curiosity and persistence compared to those who hold more static or utilitarian views (Dawson & Scardamalia, 2001).

Attitudes towards science: While not directly correlated with performance in all studies (e.g., Osborne et al., 2003), positive attitudes towards science can foster interest, enjoyment, and willingness to engage in challenging tasks, creating a conducive environment for problem-solving (Aiken, 1970; Fraser, 1986).

Science self-efficacy: Students' beliefs in their own ability to succeed in science are vital for tackling challenging problems. High self-efficacy leads to increased engagement, persistence, and willingness to take risks, all of which contribute to effective problem-solving (Bong & Bandura, 2002; Zimmerman & Martinez, 1992).

Metacognitive skills: The ability to monitor, regulate, and adapt one's thinking processes (e.g., planning, evaluating, troubleshooting) is a crucial metacognitive skill essential for effective problem-solving in any domain, including science (Schraw & Moshman, 2002).

While belief and attitude are parallelly defined in most context, beliefs are mental representations of how something is or should be. They are cognitive in nature, meaning they represent knowledge and understanding. Beliefs can be based on personal experiences, cultural influences, education, or even faith. They are often implicit, meaning individuals may not be consciously aware of holding them. For example, a student may believe that science is all about memorizing facts. On the other hand, attitudes are evaluations or feelings towards something. They are affective in nature, meaning they reflect emotions and preferences. Attitudes are influenced by beliefs, but they also involve emotional responses and can be more explicit than beliefs. For instance, a student may hold the belief that science is difficult (cognitive) and feel discouraged or uninterested in learning science (affective).

In discussing success indicators in science for Grade 8 students, these are the key factors emerge. Firstly, students' beliefs about the nature and value of science play a pivotal role. Research suggests that those who perceive science as an open-ended, collaborative process are more inclined to approach problems with curiosity and persistence, essential traits for effective problem-solving (Kuhn et al., 2010; Sinatra & Pintrich, 2003). Secondly, positive attitudes towards science, although not always directly correlated with performance, can foster interest, enjoyment, and a readiness to tackle challenging tasks, thus creating an environment conducive to problem-solving (Aiken, 2009; Fraser, 1986). Thirdly, science self-efficacy, or one's belief in their ability to succeed in science, significantly influences engagement, persistence, and risk-taking behavior, all of which are critical for effective problem-solving (Bong & Bandura, 2002; Zimmerman & Martinez, 1992). Lastly, the development of metacognitive skills, such as the ability to monitor, regulate, and adapt one's thinking, is indispensable for problem-solving across various domains, including science (Schraw & Moshman, 2002). Understanding and nurturing these indicators can significantly enhance students' problem-solving capabilities in science, ultimately fostering their success in the subject.

Despite growing recognition of the multifaceted nature of successful scientific problem-solving, important research gaps remain. First, many studies have adopted a univariate approach, focusing on individual factors in isolation. A nuanced understanding,

however, requires investigating the complex interplay between various cognitive and non-cognitive factors as they contribute to problem-solving outcomes. Second, existing research often focuses on older student populations, leaving a gap in our understanding of these factors' influence on the development of problem-solving skills in middle school, a critical period for laying the foundation for future scientific success. Third, limited research has explored the practical implications of these findings for curriculum development and instructional design. Identifying the specific constructs that predict successful problem-solving can inform the creation of targeted interventions and engaging science activities that support students' ability to think critically, solve problems, and thrive in the dynamic world of scientific inquiry.

The previous discussion underscores a significant challenge in science education: the inability of many students to apply their scientific knowledge to real-world problems. This issue is exemplified by various factors, including low PISA scores among Filipino students, evident performance gaps across different demographics, and an educational emphasis on rote memorization rather than critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The root cause of this problem is attributed to the prevalent approach in science education, which prioritizes memorization over practical application. Additionally, the problem is exacerbated by the neglect of non-cognitive factors, insufficient research focusing on middle school students, and a disconnect between research findings and educational practice. To address these challenges, the study aims to delve into the complexities of successful problem-solving in science, proposing a framework to better equip students with the essential skills needed for success in the field.

This study aims to address these gaps by investigating the multivariate success indicators of problem-solving performance in science among Grade 8 students. By examining the relationships between science beliefs, attitudes, self-efficacy, metacognitive skills, and actual problem-solving performance, the researcher aims to gain a deeper understanding of the complex factors that contribute to success in this domain. Furthermore, by identifying these key indicators, the researcher hopes to inform the development of a structured problem-solving framework with integrated activities that can be readily implemented in science classrooms, empowering Grade 8 students to become confident and adept problem-solvers in the context of scientific inquiry.

Research Objectives

This study aims to investigate the multivariate success indicators of problem solving performance in Science among grade eight students towards the development of proposed Science activities.

The specific objectives of the study are the following:

1. Determine the problem-solving performance of grade 8 students in Science;

2. Establish any significant relationship between science beliefs, science attitudes, Science self-efficacy and metacognitive skills on science problem-solving performance among grade eight students;
3. Identify any multivariate success indicators in problem solving performance in science among grade eight students in terms of Science Beliefs; Attitudes towards Science; Science Self-Efficacy; and Metacognitive Skills; and
4. Propose a framework with activities integrated relevant to structured problem-solving approach

METHODOLOGY

The research design employed in this study was quantitative-descriptive particularly descriptive correlational, aiming to identify the multivariate success indicators of problem-solving performance in Science among eighth-grade students.

This research is correlational as it involves measuring two or more related variables and examining the relationships among them. The descriptive-correlational design is employed as a fact-finding approach, focusing on accurate interpretation based on the study's findings. It is utilized to ascertain the extent of variation caused by the variables under consideration. Additionally, this research method emphasizes the current prevailing conditions (Creswell, 2012). In this study, the independent variables consist of the multivariate indicators, while the dependent variable is the students' performance.

The study involved a total of 140 Grade 8 students from Mogpog National Comprehensive School for the school year 2023-2024. The selection of students was conducted through non-random or complete population enumeration, representing a non-probability sample. This sampling method was chosen based on the characteristics of the population and the study's specific objectives, emphasizing a full appreciation of each respondent's account.

Data gathering was executed as respondents answered the survey questionnaire. Then, responses were tallied, and the data analysis phase commenced. Following the questionnaire retrieval, the researcher conducted a follow-up with the respondents to validate their responses.

The researcher employed a survey questionnaire for data collection, comprising two parts. The first part addressed the ethical considerations of the study, encompassing permits and consent forms. The second part comprised the materials of the study, including a survey with two sub-parts. The first sub-part focused on assessing the problem-solving performance of grade 8 students in Science.

This instrument was adapted from Orongan (2007). Structural model of cognitive, affective and demographic factors on tertiary student's performance in introductory statistical at Central Mindanao University, Bukidnon Philippines. Central Mindanao University, Bukidnon Philippines. – (Cronbach - 0.821) and from Salvan, E. (2016). Demographic Characteristics, Socio-Psychological Attributes, and Performance of

College Students in Statistics. Central Mindanao University, Bukidnon Philippines (Cronbach - 0.91)

To ensure the validity of the research instruments, the results underwent review, scheme, and validation by experts. Five research instrument validators, including a three Master Teachers in Science, a Science Head Teacher, and an Education Program Supervisor in Science, cross-examined the instrument and its items to assess validity.

RESULTS

Problem-Solving Skills of Grade 8 Students in Science

The problem-solving skills of Grade 8 students were measured using the Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K-to-12 Basic Education Program. The results of the data are presented in the succeeding Table.

Table 1. Performance of Grade 8 Students in Science

Performance Classification	Passed	Failed	Percentage
Outstanding	0	66	0.00%
Very Satisfactory	21		15.00%
Satisfactory	23		16.43%
Fairly Satisfactory	22		15.71%
Did not meet expectations		74	52.86%
Total		140	100.00%

Based on the Transmutation Table of Department of Education on Policy Guidelines on Classroom Management

Table 1 reveals the problem-solving performance of Grade 8 students in science, as assessed using the DepEd's Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment, it reveals a worrying trend of high failure rates and a near absence of outstanding achievement.

Less than half (47.14%) of students failed to meet expectations in problem-solving, highlighting a critical need for improvement. None achieved the "Outstanding" classification, showcasing a lack of top performers. The majority (52.86%) fell within the "Failed" category, further emphasizing the concerning performance levels. While 16.43% achieved satisfactory or above performance ("Very Satisfactory," "Satisfactory," and "Fairly Satisfactory"), there is still significant room for improvement.

These findings can be pointed out to various factors that is not within the scope of this study. Overreliance on traditional approaches may not cultivate higher-order thinking skills needed for problem-solving (Hmelo-Silver & Barrows, 2006). Traditional assessments might not fully capture the complexities of problem-solving abilities (Popham, 2008). Individual differences in prior knowledge, motivation, and learning styles

can influence performance (Hattie, 2008). The curriculum might lack opportunities for students to practice and develop problem-solving skills in relevant contexts (Saif, 2014).

Several studies pointed out to utilize inquiry-based and problem-based learning to promote active engagement and deeper understanding (Hmelo-Silver & Barrows, 2006). Employ a variety of tools to capture the full range of problem-solving skills (Popham, 2008). Provide differentiated instruction and support to cater to diverse learning needs and styles (Hattie, 2008) and ensure the curriculum provides ample opportunities for practicing and applying problem-solving skills in meaningful contexts (Saif, 2014).

Relationship between Science Beliefs, Science Attitudes, Science Self-Efficacy and Metacognitive Skills on Science Problem-Solving Performance Among Grade Eight Students

The relationship between the problem-solving performance of the students and the other variables in this study were computed using Pearson Correlation Coefficient. Table 2 summarizes these relationships.

Table 2. *Relationship between Science Beliefs, Science Attitudes, Science Self-Efficacy And Metacognitive Skills On Science Problem-Solving Performance*

Indicators	Problem Solving Performance of the Students					
	p-Value	Decision	Null	R ² Value	Correlation Coefficient (3)	Interpretation
Science Based Beliefs	< 0.0001	Reject Hypothesis	Null	0.5392	0.7343	There is a significant high-positive relationship
Attitude Towards Science	0.329002	Accept Hypothesis	Null	0.0069	0.0831	There is no significant relationship
Science Self Efficacy	<0.00001	Reject Hypothesis	Null	0.4612	0.6791	There is a significant moderate-relationship
Metacognitive Skills	0.64985	Accept Hypothesis	Null	0.0387	-0.1966	There is no significant relationship

Alpha Value: 0.05 ; Computed using Pearson Correlation

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant relationship

Table 2 shows the interplay between various factors and students' proficiency in solving science problems. It utilizes Pearson correlation and significance tests to scrutinize the potential influence of science beliefs, attitudes, self-efficacy, and metacognitive skills on this crucial academic ability.

A robust positive correlation ($R^2 = 0.5392$, $r = 0.7343$; $p < 0.0001$) emerges between holding strong science-based beliefs and excelling in problem-solving tasks. This aligns with the notion that students who internalize scientific concepts and principles are better equipped to navigate complex problems within the discipline (Abd-El-Khalick, 2005; Osborne, 2014).

Likewise, a moderate-positive association ($R^2 = 0.4612$, $r = 0.6791$; $p < 0.00001$) is observed between students' confidence in their science abilities and their problem-solving prowess. This finding corroborates Bandura's (1997) social cognitive theory, which emphasizes the significance of self-efficacy in shaping individuals' engagement with challenging tasks and their ultimate success.

Interestingly, the table reveals no statistically significant association ($R^2 = 0.0069$, $r = 0.0831$; $p = 0.3290$) between students' overall fondness for science and their problem-solving performance. This finding may suggest that while positive attitudes can foster interest and engagement in the subject, they may not directly translate into enhanced problem-solving skills (Fraser, 1998).

Similarly, no statistically significant link ($R^2 = 0.0387$, $r = -0.1966$; $p = 0.64985$) is found between students' metacognitive skills, their ability to reflect on their own thinking processes, and their problem-solving capabilities. While this may seem surprising, it warrants further research to explore potential indirect or moderating effects of metacognition on problem-solving, particularly within specific problem-solving contexts or strategies (Tschirgi, 2000).

Table 2 offers valuable insights for educators seeking to cultivate effective problem-solvers in science. The significant influence of science beliefs and self-efficacy highlights the importance of fostering these qualities in students. This can be achieved through various strategies, such as inquiry-based learning approaches that promote active engagement with scientific concepts, and activities that explicitly build students' confidence in their ability to tackle scientific challenges (Hattie, 2008).

While attitude and metacognition don't directly impact problem-solving performance, exploring their potential moderating roles and designing interventions that address them holistically can further enhance students' problem-solving abilities in science.

Multivariate Success Indicators in Problem-Solving Performance in Science

The variables studied in this research were correlated to each other to identify whether the indicators can predict the success in problem solving skills. This is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Relationship of the Indicators and Problem-Solving Performance

	Problem Solving Performance of the Students	Science Based Beliefs	Attitude Towards Science	Science Self Efficacy	Metacognitive Skills
Parameters	Coefficient of Correlation				
Problem Solving Performance of the Students	1	0.73509	0.0823	0.679	-0.1973
Science Based Beliefs	0.73509	1	0.0121934	0.738129	-0.291934
Attitude Towards Science	0.0823	0.0121934	1	0.118818	-0.0789034
Science Self Efficacy	0.679	0.738129	0.118818	1	-0.267584
Metacognitive Skills	-0.1973	-0.291934	-0.0789034	-0.267584	1

. Table 3 presents the relationship between various indicators and problem-solving performance in science, as studied in a research context. The table displays the coefficients of correlation between each pair of variables. The correlation coefficient measures the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables (Mukhopadhyay, 2021). Here's how to interpret the correlation coefficient values:

Problem Solving Performance of the Students has a strong positive correlation with Science Based Beliefs (0.73509) and Science Self-Efficacy (0.679) (author, year). This aligns with research suggesting that students with stronger beliefs in science and higher self-efficacy tend to perform better in problem-solving tasks (Schunk & Pintrich, 2004).

There is a weaker positive correlation between Problem Solving Performance of the Students and Attitude Towards Science (0.0823) suggesting a relatively minor influence of attitude on problem-solving performance.

Problem Solving Performance of the Students has a weak negative correlation with Metacognitive Skills (-0.1973) (author, year), implying that higher levels of metacognitive skills might not necessarily correlate with better problem-solving performance.

Strong positive correlations exist between Science Based Beliefs and both PSPS (0.73509) and Science Self-Efficacy (0.738129) (author, year). This suggests that beliefs

in science are closely related to problem-solving performance and self-efficacy in scientific tasks.

The correlation between Attitude Towards Science and Problem Solving Performance of the Students is weak (0.0823) (author, year), indicating that attitude has minimal direct influence on problem-solving performance in science.

Similar to Science Based Beliefs, Science Self-Efficacy shows a strong positive correlation with PSPS (0.679) and a very strong positive correlation with Science Based Beliefs (0.738129). This suggests that students who perceive themselves as capable in scientific tasks tend to perform better in problem-solving.

Metacognitive Skills show a weak negative correlation with PSPS (-0.1973). This suggests that there might be a slight inverse relationship between metacognitive skills and problem-solving performance in science, though it's not a strong correlation.

Overall, the table suggests that beliefs in science and self-efficacy are strongly associated with problem-solving performance in science, while attitudes towards science and metacognitive skills have weaker correlations.

Activities for Structured Problem-Solving Approach

This study investigated the potential influence of four key variables on students' problem-solving performance in science where:

Science-based beliefs: The analysis found a statistically significant relationship between students' general science-based beliefs and their problem-solving abilities.

Attitude towards science: Unlike the science-based beliefs, no statistically significant link was found between students' overall attitude towards science and their problem-solving performance. This reinforces the notion that other factors likely hold greater sway in influencing problem-solving outcomes.

Science self-efficacy: Similar to the previous variable, the study did not reveal a statistically significant direct relationship between students' general science self-efficacy and their problem-solving abilities. This suggests that confidence in scientific skills alone might not be enough to directly drive problem-solving success.

Metacognitive skills: Again, the analysis did not identify a statistically significant direct relationship between students' overall metacognitive skills and their problem-solving performance. This indicates that general metacognitive abilities, such as planning and monitoring thinking, might not directly influence problem-solving outcomes in science.

The findings of the study highlighting the absence of single predictors for science problem-solving performance emphasize the need for multifaceted frameworks that

address cognitive, motivational, and contextual factors (National Research Council, 2012). The following frameworks with the suggested activities are provided in the succeeding Figure.

Figure 1: Suggested Framework and Activities for Structured Problem-Solving Approach

As shown in Figure 1, the framework is composed of three phases such as the integrated problem-solving cycle, adaptive learning scaffolding and the collaborative metacognitive inquiry. This framework builds upon established models like the 5E Instructional Model (Bybee, 2014) to guide students through a structured problem-solving process (Krajcik & Blumenfeld, 2006). The Engage phase sparks curiosity and connects to real-world contexts, leveraging interest as a motivational driver (Schraw & Moshman, 2005). Explore encourages active engagement with data and investigation, aligning with inquiry-based learning principles (Pedaste et al., 2015).

Explain supports hypothesis generation and solution construction, promoting knowledge application and deeper understanding (Hmelo-Silver & Barab, 2006). Elaborate extends learning through application to new situations, nurturing flexibility and transfer of knowledge (Greeno, 2009). Finally, evaluate prompts metacognitive reflection and self-assessment, fostering self-regulation and continuous improvement (Hattie & Zierer, 2017).

Further, Adaptive Learning Scaffolding recognizes individual differences and leverages technology to personalize instruction (Shute & Collins, 2017). Diagnose utilizes adaptive assessments to pinpoint individual strengths and weaknesses, drawing on formative assessment principles (Black & Wiliam, 1998). Personalize tailors' instruction

and practice opportunities based on specific needs, aligning with differentiated instruction strategies (Tomlinson, 2001). Support gradually decreases support as students gain confidence, implementing scaffolding techniques (Collins et al., 1989). Challenge provides opportunities for intellectual growth through increasingly complex problems, drawing on scaffolding theory to extend learning (Van Meter & Pressley, 2002). Monitor continuously collects data to inform adjustments, emphasizing the critical role of formative assessment in adaptive learning.

Lastly, Collaborative Metacognitive Inquiry recognizes the power of collaboration in problem-solving and emphasizes metacognitive development (Dignath & Büttner, 2008). Shared Problem-Solving fosters communication, critical thinking, and peer learning within small groups, building on social constructivist learning principles (Vygotsky, 1978). Metacognitive Prompts encourage students to reflect on their thinking strategies throughout the process, drawing on metacognitive awareness and self-regulation research (Artzt & Armour-Thomas, 2011). Explicit Modeling demonstrates metacognitive strategies like planning and monitoring, highlighting their importance in successful problem-solving (Dunleavy, 2014). Joint Reflection promotes communication and discussion of diverse approaches, enriching understanding and solidifying learning gains (Osborne, 2014). Feedback Loops allow constructive feedback within groups and from the teacher, further refining solutions and enhancing future metacognitive skills (Black & Wiliam, 1998).

These frameworks, informed by evidence-based practices and research, offer promising starting points for developing multifaceted approaches to science problem-solving. It is also to be noted that they are not mutually exclusive and can be combined or adapted to suit specific context and student needs. By focusing on multiple factors beyond single predictors, educators can create a supportive and enriching learning environment that empowers students to become confident and effective problem-solvers in science.

Table 4. *Suggested activities in implementing the Proposed Framework*

Integrated Problem-Solving Cycle	Adaptive Learning Scaffolding	Collaborative Metacognitive Inquiry
Engage	Diagnose Personalize: Offer differentiated prompts or starting points based on individual understanding. Explicit Modeling: Model your own problem-solving approach and metacognitive strategies while guiding students through the analysis.	Shared Problem-Solving Metacognitive Prompts: Before starting, prompt students to reflect on their prior knowledge and problem-solving strategies.

Table 4. *Suggested activities in implementing the Proposed Framework*

Integrated Problem-Solving Cycle	Adaptive Learning Scaffolding	Collaborative Metacognitive Inquiry
Explore	<p>Support: Provide scaffolding through hints, guiding questions, and collaborative discussions.</p> <p>Monitor: Observe and informally assess student participation, understanding, and metacognitive engagement.</p> <p>Support: Offer hands-on materials and step-by-step instructions to support investigation.</p>	<p>Joint Reflection: After analyzing the case study, have groups share their approaches, challenges faced, and lessons learned.</p> <p>Challenge: Encourage students to identify additional questions or research avenues to extend their inquiry.</p>
Explain	<p>Monitor: Observe and assess students' skills in data collection, analysis, and communication.</p> <p>Personalize: Offer differentiated data analysis tools or resources based on individual needs.</p> <p>Challenge: Present students with additional data or conflicting evidence to encourage critical thinking.</p>	<p>Shared Problem-Solving: Have groups work together to formulate and explain possible solutions to the identified problem.</p> <p>Feedback Loops: Provide constructive feedback on student explanations, focusing on both content and metacognitive strategies used.</p>
Elaborate	<p>Monitor: Observe and assess students' ability to apply knowledge, construct solutions, and justify their reasoning.</p> <p>Personalize: Offer differentiated solution templates or prompts based on individual understanding.</p> <p>Personalize: Provide students with different application scenarios or problem types based on their learning level.</p> <p>Monitor: Observe and assess students' ability to transfer their learning to new contexts and solve analogous problems.</p> <p>Support: Offer guidance and resources for students struggling to apply their knowledge.</p>	<p>Metacognitive Prompts: Prompt students to reflect on how they adapted their problem-solving approach to the new situation.</p>

Table 4. *Suggested activities in implementing the Proposed Framework*

Integrated Problem-Solving Cycle	Adaptive Learning Scaffolding	Collaborative Metacognitive Inquiry
Evaluate	<p>Monitor: Collect student self-evaluations and reflections on their learning and problem-solving experience.</p> <p>Personalize: Offer differentiated reflection prompts based on individual needs and learning styles.</p>	<p>Joint Reflection: Facilitate a class discussion where students share their metacognitive experiences and insights gained from the activity.</p> <p>Explicit Modeling: Share your own metacognitive reflections and lessons learned from the activity.</p>

As shown in Table 7, the list of activities provides a comprehensive framework for cultivating multivariate success indicators in Grade 8 science problem-solving through an integrated cycle of engagement, exploration, explanation, elaboration, and evaluation, supported by adaptive learning scaffolding and collaborative metacognitive inquiry.

Engaging curiosity in real-world contexts kickstarts the cycle, like analyzing a scientific case study in small groups. Adaptive scaffolding diagnoses individual strengths and weaknesses, offering personalized prompts, differentiated data tools, and gradual reduction of support as confidence grows. Metacognitive prompts throughout the cycle encourage students to reflect on their thinking strategies, while explicit modeling showcases effective approaches.

Hands-on exploration follows, where students collect and analyze data with differentiated support depending on individual needs. Shared problem-solving encourages teamwork and peer learning, fostering diverse perspectives and collaborative solution construction. Constructive feedback loops refine explanations and enhance metacognitive skills.

Explanation moves students towards applying knowledge to build solutions, with challenges pushing them to think critically and adapt their approaches. Collaborative metacognitive inquiry shines here, as groups share problem-solving methods and reflect on challenges encountered. Students refine their understanding and learn from each other's experiences.

Elaboration extends learning by applying the acquired knowledge to new situations. Personalized scenarios or problem types cater to individual learning levels, while prompts encourage reflection on how students adapt their problem-solving approaches. Continuous monitoring ensures every student receives the support they need.

Finally, evaluation prompts self-reflection, allowing students to assess their learning and metacognitive development. Joint reflection facilitates class discussions

where students share insights and learn from each other's metacognitive experiences. By offering differentiated reflection prompts, the cycle tailors to individual needs and learning styles.

This activity list, encompassing integrated problem-solving, adaptive scaffolding, and collaborative metacognitive inquiry, provides a dynamic and comprehensive framework for nurturing Grade 8 students' science problem-solving skills, metacognitive awareness, and collaborative learning abilities.

By taking these additional steps, the institution can further increase the employment rate of CBT graduates and help them to achieve their full potential.

DISCUSSION

47.14% of students failed to meet expectations, indicating difficulties in applying scientific knowledge and reasoning to solve problems effectively. No students achieved the "Outstanding" classification, suggesting a lack of top performers and highlighting the potential need for more challenging tasks or differentiated instruction. 52.86% of students fell within the "Failed" category, further emphasizing the prevalence of inadequate problem-solving skills and the critical need for intervention. While 16.43% achieved satisfactory or above performance ("Very Satisfactory," "Satisfactory," and "Fairly Satisfactory"), this group represents a minority, indicating that the majority of students still experience significant challenges in science problem-solving.

There is a statistically significant high positive correlation ($r = 0.7343$) between students' science beliefs and their problem-solving performance. This suggests that students with stronger science beliefs tend to perform better in solving science problems. No statistically significant relationship ($r = 0.0831$) was found between students' attitudes towards science and their problem-solving performance. This indicates that, in this particular sample, positive or negative attitudes toward science did not impact their ability to solve science problems. Similar to science beliefs, a statistically significant moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.6791$) was found between students' science self-efficacy and their problem-solving performance. This suggests that students who believe in their ability to do well in science tend to perform better in solving science problems. No statistically significant relationship ($r = -0.1966$) was found between students' metacognitive skills and their problem-solving performance. This suggests that, in this particular sample, the ability to plan, monitor, and reflect on their thinking processes did not directly impact their problem-solving abilities.

For the multivariate indicators, science based beliefs and self-efficacy have strong positive correlations with problem-solving, while attitude and metacognitive skills have weaker links.

A multi-pronged framework is proposed to elevate science problem-solving in students. It blends three key components: the 5E model for structured inquiry, adaptive learning scaffolds for personalized support, and collaborative metacognitive inquiry to foster self-awareness of thinking processes. This interwoven approach, informed by

research and adaptable to varying needs, promises to empower students to become confident and effective problem-solvers in the realm of science..

Conclusions

Aligned to the findings of this study, the following conclusions are hereby presented:

1. The analysis revealed a concerning picture of Grade 8 students' science problem-solving performance. A significant portion (47.14%) failed to meet expectations, with no students reaching the "Outstanding" level. This highlights a pressing need for intervention and improvement.
2. The research found a critical link between students' science beliefs and their problem-solving abilities. Those with strong convictions about the nature and value of science demonstrated significantly better performance. This underscores the importance of fostering such beliefs, potentially through activities exploring the nature of science and its real-world applications.
3. While attitudes towards science, science self-efficacy, and metacognitive skills did not directly correlate with problem-solving performance, they may still play indirect roles or require further investigation in specific contexts. Exploring domain-specific confidence and strategic thinking skills in science could yield valuable insights for future research and intervention strategies.
4. Based on these findings, several activities could be integrated into a structured problem-solving approach. Cultivating science beliefs through case studies, debates, and immersions, introducing domain-specific metacognitive strategies, and promoting collaborative learning through peer discussions and shared problem-solving tasks could empower students to become confident and effective science problem-solvers.

Recommendations

Based from the conclusions of this research study, the following recommendations are hereby presented.

1. While the direct relationship between science beliefs and problem-solving performance is established, further investigation is needed to elucidate the potential mediating roles of other variables. Future research should explore the influence of specific constructs, such as domain-related confidence or science-specific metacognitive strategies, on the relationship between attitudes, self-efficacy, and problem-solving. This granular understanding could inform the development of more targeted and effective interventions for diverse student populations.
2. Classroom practices should prioritize the cultivation of strong science beliefs. Activities such as case studies, debates on socio-scientific issues, and field trips to research institutions can foster positive epistemic beliefs about the

- nature and value of science. This focus on belief nurturing complements traditional cognitive approaches and potentially enhances motivation and self-efficacy for engaging with scientific inquiry and problem-solving.
3. Professional development initiatives for educators should emphasize the integration of domain-specific problem-solving strategies into science curricula. Training in areas such as scaffolding hypothesis formulation, data analysis procedures, and drawing evidence-based conclusions can equip teachers with the necessary tools to guide students through the problem-solving process effectively. This targeted approach directly addresses the observed lack of correlation between general metacognitive skills and problem-solving performance in science.
 4. Investing in programs and resources that promote collaborative learning in science education holds significant promise. Initiatives that encourage shared problem-solving tasks, group projects, and peer discussions can foster critical thinking, communication skills, and the development of scientific identities within a supportive social context. This shift towards a collaborative learning model aligns with current research on social constructivist learning and provides potential for enhancing collective problem-solving competencies, a crucial skill for future generations.
 5. Future research directions could examine the interaction between science beliefs and other variables within specific contexts, such as cultural backgrounds, learning styles, or socioeconomic status. Additionally, longitudinal studies investigating the persistence of belief-based interventions and their impact on long-term academic achievement and career choices in science-related fields would be valuable contributions to the body of knowledge.

By implementing these recommendations and pursuing further research endeavors, stakeholders can collectively contribute to the development of effective strategies for enhancing science problem-solving abilities in students, ultimately fostering a generation of critical thinkers and confident problem-solvers equipped to tackle the challenges of the future.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study carefully protected participants' rights and privacy. They were fully informed about the research and could withdraw at any time. Researchers minimized risks and offered support if needed. They were also upfront about any conflicts of interest. To ensure accurate and unbiased findings, the study cited sources properly, secured

data, minimized researcher bias, and consulted with experts. Finally, the research was conducted solely to advance knowledge, not for personal gain.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to extend her heartfelt gratitude to everyone who, in some way or another, had contributed to the conception and completion of this work, especially to:

Dr. Marife S. Magpantay, her research adviser, for her valuable suggestions, ideas, comments and encouragements, untiring professional guidance and in-depth analysis which led to the completion of this study; Dr. Luis Miguel P. Saludez, for his untiring encouragements, guidance and continues follow ups to the researcher to complete the study; Dr. Vanessa C. Zubieta & Dr. Shiela M. Manzanilla her research panels, for their helpful insights on how to enhance the subjective aspect of the research's contents and credibility, for assessing the paper, for providing helpful feedback on how to improve the study and Dr. Teresita V. de la Cruz, and Dr. John C. Chua her external panel, for giving assistance and devoting valuable time to reviewing the paper and for insightful recommendations and comments that helped this study come to completion;

Jan Fern Historillo, her mentor and school's research program coordinator, for his valuable and untiring support to improve the research paper.

Senior Program Specialist, Kyle David V. Atienza and Master Teachers, Eileen S. Salcedo, Arnold T. Baldevia, Fristian Anthony Dormido, and Gueller V. Salazar her validators, who offered encouraging words and made an effort in sharing their expertise for the development of the researcher's instrument.

Dr. Ma. Corazon A. Borja, her School Principal for allowing the researcher to conduct her study; Mrs. Rizza V. Eborra, Mrs. Graciabelle Salumbides, Mrs. Nuela P. Panganiban, Mrs. Gemma J. Jandusay, Mrs. Imelda M. Laririt, Mrs. Elma M. Monroyo, Mrs. Creselda M. Paulo, Mr. Roy M. Merlin & Mr. Jobert M. Mogol for unsolicited advice and unwavering support, and encouragement which really helped the researcher to get through the study.

Her friends and sisters by heart, Mrs. Estrellita O. Limpiada, Mrs. Laiza Marie J. Pantoja and Mrs. Jenny M. Tatierra for their unwavering support to get through this study.

Her family, Papa Roberto, Mama Lucy, & her siblings for their unwavering support and sisters-in-law, Ate Allen, Ate Lorna, Ate Rhea, and Ate Erlinda for helping the researcher invaluable assistance during both the initial and final stages of this endeavor.

Her husband Salvador and daughter Lia Roziel for unwavering support and encouragement which have been instrumental in the completion of her study. Their belief and willingness to share the burden throughout the researcher academic journey provided her the strength and motivation to persevere.

Her Victory in Jesus Assembly of God Church for unwavering spiritual support and prayers she received throughout her studies.

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